

**Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for
Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of
Resources from the end-of-use built environment**

DISCOVER

D1.3 Oliwall

**WP 1. Autonomous non-invasive scanning and
identification system (M1 – M18)**

WP Leader: UPC

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CSV format	Comma-Separated Values format
EtherCAT	Ethernet for Control Automation Technology
FDTD	Finite-Difference Time-Domain
FSM	Finite-State Machine
GPR	Ground-Penetrating Radar
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
OAK camera	OpenCV AI Kit camera
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
ROS 2	Robot Operating System 2
RTAB-Map	Real-Time Appearance-Based Mapping
YOLO	You Only Look Once (real-time object detection algorithm)

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About the DISCOVER project

DISCOVER aims to develop an autonomous, synchronous, continuous and intelligent identification and data analysis system for materials and products in existing end-of-life built works. The proposed approach will provide key stakeholders, including academia research performers, along with construction industry representatives, with data-driven insights to make deconstruction more efficient, optimise the use of resources, improve the environmental footprints and enhance the circularity of construction and demolition, unlocking the potential of end-of-life built works, which will become material banks. The expected outcomes include an autonomous robotic platform coupled with continuous identification tools to scan built works and provide synchronous quantitative and qualitative data from different materials, including complex and concealed elements. Artificial intelligence algorithms will allow a rapid analysis of the properties and characteristics of components, and feed the automated scan-to-BIM model creation. The multi-dimensional BIM, including selective demolition processes, labour productivity, and technical planning, will become a Digital Twin of the demolition site optimised by social, economic, and environmental multi-criteria assessments. This approach will highly contribute to significantly increasing the supply of traceable and sustainable construction materials and products for enhancing their wider market acceptance, following the waste hierarchy. The social impacts of digital transformation in the construction sector will be considered, and also new professional development tools for the relevant stakeholders will be proposed. The system will be tested in 4 different real demolition sites (Spain, Portugal, Poland and Belgium), offering a complete range of built work typologies and wide geographical coverage to demonstrate the replicability potential of DISCOVER, increasing the project dissemination capacity and awareness among the construction sector.

Abstract

This report contains the information on the creation of the Oliwall robot, and the links to the different materials composing it: to software repositories, images and videos of the robot, and operation and maintenance manual.

The robot is the physical embodiment for the application of the results of the tasks in WP1 on demolition sites. The system is validated in a controlled real environment, which is the UPC-CDEI laboratory for mobile robot. The integrated results include robot navigation and mapping, identification of building geometry, integration of RGB-based sensor for identification of building elements, and integration of the software for GPR and hyperspectral cameras. The current user interface is also presented.

1. Introduction

This document contains the information on the Oliwall robot, deliverable 1.3 (D1.3) of the DISCOVER project (HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-11-101129909).

1.1. Work package 1

WP1 encompasses tasks essential to create the functional Oliwall robot prototype. Oliwall is a mobile manipulator robot, whose task is to autonomously navigate buildings and infrastructure, continuously collecting data about spaces, elements, and materials without invasive testing. The sensors allow for characterization of both visible elements and materials, as well as those hidden within the structure.

The key objectives of this work package are:

- The design of the Oliwall robot according to the needs and requirements of the construction sector, especially adapted to operate in demolition environments.
- The development and implementation of the non-invasive identification techniques for data collection, which will be based on vision sensors, GPR and LiDAR.
- The construction of the prototype robot and the user interface, and its validation in a controlled environment.

1.2.1. Deliverable 1.3. Oliwall

Within the objectives of WP1, the Deliverable 1.3 includes the results on:

- Pass from design to implementation through the construction of the Oliwall robot, a fully-functional, industrial-grade prototype.
- Implementation of the software for the navigation, localization, planning and sensing with the different sensors, and integration in the robot stack. Presentation of the interaction with the user.
- Testing of the system in the controlled environment of the UPC-CDEI mobile robotics laboratory.

1.2. Contents of the deliverable

This report contains the physical description of the robot, including mechanical and electronic parts, and the description of the software that drives the behavior of the robot. We also include the results of the tests that show every part of the system performing satisfactorily.

The appendices contain the manual of the robot and additional software and hardware information.

2. Oliwall robot hardware: design and implementation

The Oliwall robot is a mobile platform with an arm manipulator (a mobile manipulator) designed to fulfill the following functions: navigate in the demolition environment, identify the elements to explore, and apply different sensors in order to determine and locate objects that can appear in the demolition site and materials that compose the different parts of the site. All this information is to be stored and transmitted to the BIM.

2.1. Oliwall design specifications

Oliwall is an omnidirectional mobile manipulator developed for the DISCOVER project. A brief summary of Oliwall characteristics is presented below.

In its design specifications, Oliwall's total planar dimensions are 814x612 mm, which are the maximum possible to ensure the robot can go through most corridors and make a 90° turn while maximizing the robot's stability.

The mounted manipulator arm is a commercial UR10e robot from Universal Robots. This arm is mounted on a lifting column, so that the total height of the robot can be up to 3,2m, to reach high ceilings. Its slender built means that stability will be an issue that is carefully considered. The omnidirectional robot base is powered by three motors, making it possible for the robot to move instantaneously in any direction. Its total weight is around 275 kg. The robot has protection IP52C.

The main components of the robot are shown in Table 1.

Component/Assembly	Weight (Kg)
Battery	60
Battery supporting structure	8
UR10	33.5
Lifting column	30
UR10 control box	4.5
Electronics and sensors	36
Wheel assemblies	25
Base structure	15
Toothed crown and pinion actuator	20
“Universal joint” mechanism	6
Steel structure	30
Scanning sensors	8
TOTAL	276

Table 1. Components of the Oliwall robot.

The robot can navigate at a speed of 1m/s and overcome slopes of up to 30%. The ground clearance of the robot is 45 mm, which defines the maximum height of obstacles it can

overcome. To ensure safe pathing, an obstacle deflector has been added to the front to clear larger obstacles from the robot's path (see Figure 1), protecting the robot from the debris often present in demolition sites. Other, bigger obstacles, can be avoided using the path planner.

Figure 1. Robot at the maximum 30% slope; detail of the basis clearance.

Figure 2 shows the overall design and the workspace of the robot.

Figure 2. Oliwall robot with its workspace.

The sensors' plate contains the ground-penetrating radar (GPR), an RGB-D OAK camera, a hyperspectral camera, and some range sensors to keep the parallel distance between plate and wall. The metal detector, that was considered a possible addition, will not be finally added. Figure 3 shows the final implementation of the sensors' plate.

Figure 3. Sensors' plate at the end effector of the robot.

2.2. Components and construction of Oliwall

In this section we describe the main functional blocks of the robot and their implementation on Oliwall. We include CAD drawings as well as pictures of the assembly process.

2.2.1. Oliwall base

As shown in Figure 4, the base consists of two motor-reducer assemblies responsible for traction and a supporting caster wheel. This part also includes the motor drivers and the pinion motor and reducer that will actuate the toothed crown located at the top. This toothed crown is responsible for rotating the upper structure with respect to the base in order to ensure omnidirectionality.

Figure 4. Oliwall base, design and implementation.

Above the crown, there is a mechanism to prevent hyperstaticity. This mechanism functions similar to a universal joint, allowing two rotations and vertical movement. The

upper structure can move freely relative to the base while fulfilling its function of increasing the robot's stability by serving as its support.

2.2.2. Oliwall structure and arm manipulator

The metallic structure contains the battery, all the electronics and sensors necessary for the proper functioning of the robot, the UR10 controller, the UR10 lifting column, and the robotic arm itself (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Oliwall structural platform and manipulator; CAD and implementation. From left to right: CAD, robot structure, robot arm and plate, elevating column, suspension system.

All these essential parts of the robot are supported in two ways. Firstly, they have four caster wheels that rest on the ground. Secondly, they are connected to the base via springs with adjustable compression. This design transfers a significant portion of the structure's weight to the driving wheels, increasing traction and reducing the load on the four auxiliary caster wheels, which primarily serve to enhance the robot's stability against movements and inclinations. Regarding the electrical power, the robot will be powered by a Deye SE-G5.1 Pro-B 51.4 V.

2.2.3. Oliwall sensors

Oliwall is equipped with navigation sensors (cameras and LiDAR) at the base, and scanning sensors, see Figure 5. The scanning sensors will be positioned at the end-effector of the UR10. The Figure 6 illustrates the placement of the sensors in its base.

Figure 6. Sensors' plate. CAD and implementation. In the picture, the plate has the range sensors at the corners, the OAK RGB-D camera, the hyperspectral sensor and the GPR.

Figure 7. Figures of sensors: LiDAR + Camera for geometry calculation, sensors on plate.

The list of sensors, actuators and related electronics can be found in Table 2. The figures below show the implementation of several sensors.

Equipment	Model
Wheel Motor	BR03, Brushless, encoder incremental
Vertical Motor	Brushless
Vertical Encoder	Absolute, multi-turn
Drivers - all	IRD_EB_48/60
Transformer 24 v	SD-1000L-29
Arm	UR10e

Vertical column	Custom LINAK
Controlbox UR10	OEM Control Box
PC	Jetson AGX orin
LiDAR Dome	OSDome
LiDAR Sick	multiScan100
IMU	Integrated at Sick
Camera	OAK-D Pro W
Multispectral camera	Custom ,Visible: 335-700 nm, no visible: 990-1700 nm
Sensor GPR	GP8800
Battery	DEYE SE-G5.1Pro-B
Switch	Teltonika RUTX50
Router	Teltonika TSW030
Vent	Axial fan RS PRO de 92.5 x 92.5 x 25mm, 24 V dc, 3.4W, 2900rpm, caudal 88.3m ³ /h, 35dB
Slip ring	H2586-2410-SMT

Table 2. Sensing and actuation equipment on robot.

2.2.4. Electronics

The Table 3 shows the electronic components in Oliwall.

Components	Voltage (V)	Nominal current (A)	Nominal Power (W)
Battery	48	50	2400
Magneto 1	48	1	50
Magneto 2	48	25	1250
Magneto 3	48	6	300
Magneto 4	48	50	2500
Electrical contactor	24	30	720
Converter	24	10	240
Drivers converter	24	10	240
Encoder	24	2	48
PC	24	5	120
Driving motors	48	16.8	805.7
Toothed crown motor	48	16.8	805.7
Drivers	24	10	240
PLC	24	3.5	84
USB	24	1.5	36
Antenna UBLOX	5	0.02	0.08
Electronics UBLOX	5	0.1	0.5
on/off switch	24	10	240
Router	24	0.3	7.2

LiDAR Dome	24	0.83	20
LiDAR electronics	24	1.5	36
Antenna GNSS	5	0.02	0.08
LED	24	0.01	0.24
Arduino	5	1	5
UR10 Controlbox	24	2	130
Lifting Column	24	6	144
LiDAR	24	0.11	2.7
Scanning sensors (GPR, cameras...)	TBD*	TBD*	TBD*

Table 3. Electronic components of the Oliwall robot.

Figure 8. Work on the assembly of the robot.

3. Oliwall robot software: definition and implementation

The Oliwall behavior is implemented in the robot stack as follows: the high-level planning is captured in a Finite-State-Machine (FSM). Its states are translated to commands for the base-arm motion and coordination, combined task planning and docking strategies. The ROS2 Nav2 package controls the navigation of the base, containing global, local planners and controller. The scanning tasks are implemented through a path planning package, the joint trajectory controller and the wall following controller.

The perception and localization package is based on fusion of LiDAR point cloud and camera's RGB information, and allows to create the map and to localize the robot within the map. For doing this, RTAB-Map 3D is used.

The communication with the actuators and sensors of the robot is realized through EtherCAT or serial communication. ROS2 drivers from the manufacturers or implemented by the team are used. This scheme, as well as the different sensors and actuators used, are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Oliwall software schematics.

Figure 11. Left, the two LiDARs used for navigation. Right, the dome LiDAR.

Localization and mapping

To map the environment for the purpose of navigation, we are using *RTAB-Map* (Real-Time Appearance-Based Mapping) combined with the dome 3D LiDAR sensor and one RGB-D camera. The raw 3D and visual data are processed and projected into a 2D occupancy grid, which serves as the basis for global navigation. This allows us to leverage the precision of 3D sensing while maintaining compatibility with 2D navigation tools.

Mapping is conducted during the initial exploration of the space, to generate a consistent and accurate floorplan of the indoor space. During this initial exploration, *RTAB-Map* creates a database with the information of all the sensors used, in this case a 3D point cloud of the environment from the LiDAR and both the color and depth images from the RGB-D camera. Also, *RTAB-Map* projects the visual (RGB) information into the 3D points, assigning a color to each one of them and generating a colored point cloud as can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Point cloud from LiDAR, without RGB fusion (left) and with RGB fusion (right).

The action of knowing the position and orientation of the robot with respect to a global reference frame is called localization. For localization, we rely on *RTAB-Map*'s odometry and SLAM modules. The odometry component estimates relative motion using LiDAR data, providing the transform between the robot's base frame and the odometry frame. Simultaneously, the SLAM component maintains global consistency by detecting loop closures using mainly visual data (color + depth) and generating the map-to-odometry

transform. The sensor fusion for both localization and navigation is handled entirely by *RTAB-Map*, directly in the odometry or SLAM modules, or with the synchronization modules that are provided, simplifying the data management while maintaining reliable pose estimation.

The autonomous exploration of the environment is done by following a **frontier-based approach**. The robot starts exploring the closest frontier and keeps exploring until there are no more frontiers (see Figure 13), or the ones that are left are smaller than the robot size, which means that the areas behind it are unfeasible to be explored (see Figure 14).

Once the exploration is finished, a second round of mapping will be automatically started to obtain denser point clouds and correct the errors on the maps, both 3D and 2D grid, by loop closure when revisiting the same places again.

Figure 13. Exploration using frontier-based approach. The robot finds the closer frontier and plans its trajectory from it while exploring new territory.

Figure 14. Unfeasible area is identified for the mapping.

Global and local path planning for the base

The global path planning consists of generating trajectories within the map to arrive at desired positions. It is handled by the *Nav2* Grid-based planner plugin, which is configured

to operate at a high update frequency. It is designed to tolerate some level of unknown space in the map and does not rely on A* but rather on a Dijkstra-based approach. This ensures robust, cost-optimal path generation across the mapped environment. The planner is tuned for responsive performance and smooth goal tracking in static and partially known indoor settings. This Navigation 2 stack is an open-source project for the ROS 2 framework, freely available on GitHub [Macenski:2020], [Macenski:2023], [Nav2:2025].

In the global planner, the grid encodes the environment as a matrix of cells, whose values represent free space (0), occupied or obstacle space (1), and unknown space (-1). Dijkstra's algorithm works by assigning costs to each cell, starting from the goal (or start, depending on implementation), and then expanding outward in all directions, updating the minimal cost to reach each cell. For more information, see [Navi-Wall:2025].

The local planner creates the behaviour to follow the path and to avoid any obstacle that could appear in the planned path. For local trajectory execution, we use the Regulated Pure Pursuit Controller or the Dynamic Window Approach (DWB) Controller. The first is used when the robot is following a differential drive mode, whereas the second is used when the omnidirectional mode is used. These controllers are configured for smooth and safe path tracking, with careful handling of velocity regulation, curvature adaptation, and rotation behaviour. Key aspects of the configuration include:

- High-frequency control updates for smooth actuation.
- Collision prediction mechanisms to ensure safe operation near obstacles.
- Dynamic adjustments to linear and angular velocity based on path curvature and distance to the goal.
- Goal-checking logic that ensures precise final positioning and orientation.

These settings provide a balance between agility and stability, making the controller well-suited for indoor navigation with tight corners and cluttered paths.

Navi-Wall navigation

For the path planning of the mobile manipulator, the *Navi-Wall* algorithms were developed and implemented. A summary is included here for completeness; see [Navi-Wall:2025] for more details.

In *Navi-Wall*, the motion planning of the base is complemented with the motion planning of the arm, and a combined docking strategy is also implemented. In addition, both arm and base will be controlled together to follow a given trajectory, with broad motion belonging to the base and using the arm to accomplish the desired proximity to the objects to be analyzed.

For the UR10 arm manipulator, a motion planning algorithm has been developed using a discretization of the reachable workspace of the robot and the A* star path finding algorithm (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. Precomputed workspace of the robotic arm.

For this first version of *Navi-Wall*, the scanning of the walls or columns is performed after the base docks in the optimal calculated position (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. Optimized base location for the reach of the arm.

3.3. Oliwall control

For the omnidirectional base, a custom ROS2 hardware interface has been developed specifically for this application. This platform ensures full compatibility with any standard ROS2 controller by abstracting the details of the hardware implementation. At the hardware level, the base relies on three *Infranor* IRD-eb-48/60 drives. These drives use the EtherCAT communication protocol, enabling its connection directly to the robot's computer, through a switch, avoiding any intermediary between the servo drives and the ROS2 control infrastructure.

Within this configuration, the robot's computer gathers the real-time feedback from the motors, including encoder tick counts and estimated velocities, and forwarding this information to the ROS2 software via the hardware interface, which communicates with the motor drives. Conversely, the motor velocity commands computed by the ROS2 controller are transmitted to the corresponding motor drivers. The motor drives' hardware interface also handles low-level error management, such as exception handling and the triggering of error flags, ensuring a safe and robust control loop. Also, it integrates the standard CiA402 device profile for drives and motor control, standardized in the IEC 61800-7, which allows for structured, real-time industrial programming.

3.4. LiDAR + RGB geometry reconstruction

To simplify the creation of a semantic map, the LiDAR point cloud is combined with color information from one or more RGB cameras. The main idea is to assign each 3D LiDAR point a corresponding color from the camera image so that the resulting point cloud contains both geometry (x,y,z) and appearance (RGB). This colored point cloud can then be used for higher-level tasks such as object recognition, classification, or scene understanding.

To achieve this, each LiDAR point is projected onto the image plane of the camera. In other words, the 3D coordinates of a point in the LiDAR frame are transformed into a 2D pixel location in the image. This process requires two types of calibration:

- Camera intrinsic calibration: Describes the internal parameters of the camera (focal length, principal point, and distortion) and defines how 3D rays are mapped to 2D pixels.
- Extrinsic calibration between the LiDAR and the camera: Describes the rigid transformation (rotation and translation) between the LiDAR coordinate frame and the camera coordinate frame. This allows expressing LiDAR points in the camera's reference frame before projection.

Figure 17. Point cloud from LiDAR with RGB fusion.

When performing this 3D-to-2D projection, multiple LiDAR points can end up mapped to the same pixel in the image plane. This happens because many points in 3D space can lie along the same viewing ray from the camera's perspective. To handle this, a depth-based filtering step is used. For each pixel, only points that are sufficiently close to the closest point along that ray are assigned the color of the corresponding pixel. Points that are much farther behind the closest point (likely occluded) are not colored, which reduces incorrect color assignments due to occlusions.

In a multi-camera setup, each LiDAR point could be visible in several different camera views. In this case, the system first determines which camera is best suited to colorize a given point. A common strategy is to select the closest camera to the point (based on the distance from the camera center to the 3D point) and use only that camera's image for the color assignment. This helps minimize projection errors and ensures more accurate color mapping, especially when cameras have overlapping fields of view.

After this procedure, each LiDAR point that could be successfully projected and validated is stored with both its geometric coordinates and its assigned color. The final output is a colored point cloud where each point has the format (x,y,z,R,G,B) . This enriched

representation serves as the basis for generating a semantic map, where additional labels (such as object categories or surface types) can be attached in later processing steps.

3.5. RGB-based object classification

The object classification is performed with the OAK camera, using the 2D sensor. The output is a bounding box for the object, and its belonging to one of these initial classes:

1. Doors,
2. Stairs,
3. Pillars,
4. Beams,
5. Pipes/Ducts,
6. Windows,
7. Radiators,
8. Light fixtures,
9. Toilet,
10. Sink,
11. Bathtub,
12. Air conditioning,
13. Air vent,
14. Tiles/Bricks

Currently the camera and the software are integrated in the robot. While navigating, the robot is identifying the members of the classes as seen in the Testing Results chapter. The Figure 18 shows the camera and an image of the identification system.

Figure 18. Camera and tests of the RGB object classification algorithm.

The objects will be georeferenced at the center of the bounding box, by projecting the image onto the point cloud. Each object, with the size of the bounding box and the 3D location of its center, will be added to the database of objects to be sent to the BIM.

3.6. Hyperspectral data acquisition

The dual hyperspectral camera sends a ray at a precise location and distance and analyzes the returning beam on two different spectrum bands. It is important to notice that this camera will only the materials present at the surface of reflection of the beam; it is, therefore, complementary to the internal analysis of the GPR and the Pokeye equipment.

The hyperspectral sensor is mounted on the sensors plate as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Multispectral sensor.

3.7. GPR-based data acquisition

The robot integrates a Proceq GP8800 ground-penetrating radar from Screening Eagle Technologies, a multifrequency system operating between 400 and 6000 MHz that enables imaging at shallow depths (typically up to 40–50 cm in concrete). Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) is a non-destructive electromagnetic technique that emits short pulses into the material and records the reflections produced when the waves encounter discontinuities. In the resulting radargrams, two main feature types are typically observed: hyperbolas, corresponding to buried objects detected as the antenna passes transversely over them (e.g., rebar, ducts, voids), and horizontal reflections, which indicate layer boundaries or material changes (see Figure 20).

Figure 20. The GPR radargram.

The GPR is remotely controlled through a dedicated Screening Eagle API (under a confidentiality agreement), allowing full configuration of acquisition parameters, including linear or meshed scan modes, line spacing, spatial resolution, and data-storage format. The workflow illustrating the operation of the robot-mounted GPR is shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. The workflow illustrating the operation of the robot-mounted GPR.

The recorded radargrams are processed using automatic feature-detection algorithms. The dataset was designed to provide training and validation data for the algorithms while also offering a controlled setting to analyse how the GPR signal reacts to different embedded structural elements. For this purpose, a diverse set of specimens was prepared, covering various materials, reinforcement layouts, and internal features, and the experimental measurements were complemented with synthetic radargrams. These synthetic data, generated with GPRMax using the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) method, enable controlled testing conditions and supply additional training material when real data are limited. An example of the dataset is shown in Table 4.

<i>Description</i>	<i>Real data</i>	<i>Simulated data</i>
Plastic tube, 4 cm diameter, buried at 5 cm depth		

Table 4. Example of the dataset for the algorithms.

The detection of hyperbolic signatures in B-scans is primarily addressed through deep-learning-based object detection. YOLO was selected among several candidate architectures due to its favourable balance between speed and accuracy, making it suitable for real-time applications. The current model achieves a precision of 0.769 mAP (see Figure 22).

Figure 22. Detection of hyperbolas using the YOLO model.

Beyond deep-learning detection, a signal-processing pipeline was developed to extract the hyperbola equation. After YOLO identifies a region of interest, the corresponding radargram segment is extracted. All GPR data are converted into a common CSV format where columns are traces and rows are time samples. Since buried targets produce distinct amplitude extrema, the algorithm detects these peaks across traces after noise-reduction filtering. Finally, the extracted peak positions are used to fit a hyperbola, yielding its key geometric parameters (apex location, curvature, and opening). These parameters form the basis for estimating subsurface target properties, including depth and diameter (see Figure 23).

Figure 23. Peak amplitudes detected in the b-scan using the signal processing code.

Two additional analysis modules are used to characterise the properties of the buried objects. The first module focuses on material differentiation. By applying Fourier transforms to the extracted signals, the data can be analysed in the frequency domain, where clear differences in the spectral behaviour of plastic and metallic targets become apparent (see Figure 24).

A second module computes the estimated diameter of the buried object. Together, these tools provide both material classification and geometric characterization of subsurface targets.

Figure 24. Spectral difference between plastic and metal rebars.

4. Oliwall testing results

In this chapter we describe the results of the testing in the controlled laboratory environment.

The experiments are described below. They are validated through observation and recording of results, and with the results of measuring the corresponding KPIs described below:

Test 1: Navigation and mapping of the (unknown) laboratory space, with autonomous determination of the end-of-task metrics.

KPI 1.1: Scanning of at least 95% of testing site with the LiDAR.

KPI 1.2: Less than 0,002 interventions/m² during the scanning (translates to at most 1 intervention).

Results:

The system is able to map 100% of the laboratory environment (KPI1.1). See Figure 25 below with the complete scan of the space. However, we detected that a first human intervention is necessary to free the space of objects such as chairs or tables that may impede the approximation of the robot to the walls.

Besides this initial setup of the system, the robot can perform autonomously for the laboratory space, without human interventions (KPI1.2).

Test 2: Navigating the space for classification and georeferencing of construction objects.

KPI 1.2: Less than 0,002 interventions/m² during the scanning (translates to at most 1 intervention).

KPI 1.3: Not applicable here; however, for this phase, it is important that the robot is able to identify the ambiguous classification.

KPI 1.4: Georeferenced data error less than +/- 5mm.

Results: The initial version of the object classification system performs autonomously, no need for human intervention (KPI 1.2). The system does not identify ambiguous classification; however, the confidence level in the classification can be used as an indicator for this (see Figures below). We have not implemented this step yet (KPI1.3).

Regarding the georeferenced data error (KPI 1.4), this will be tested once the geometry is reconstructed with the desired precision. This is a task beyond WP1.

Test 3: Applying Navi-Wall to recognize the materials of walls, columns, ceiling and floor.

KPI 1.2: Less than 0,002 interventions/m² during the scanning (translates to at most 1 intervention).

KPI 1.3: Not applicable here; however, for this phase, it is important that the robot is able to identify the ambiguous classification.

KPI 1.4: Georeferenced data error less than +/- 5mm.

Results:

For the KPIs 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4, please see comments above.

The **RGB identification of objects** has been integrated in the robot and runs smoothly in the pipeline. The testing in the laboratory environment shows potential for a good detection; however, more data and more training is needed. The georeferencing of the objects within the map will be added to the system once the classifier arrives to the desired performance. Figure 25 shows the performance of the system in the laboratory environment.

Figure 25. Objects classified in the laboratory.

The **multispectral camera** can classify separately the concrete, plastic walls and brick walls of the laboratory environment, however, the paint represents a problem. Figure 26 shows the pictures of the testing areas, and in Figure 27 we can see the results of the analysis.

Figure 26. Walls for testing hyperspectral sensors.

Figure 27. Intensity as a function of frequency for the hyperspectral data. Distinct peaks can be seen for different materials.

The GPR sensor can identify hyperbolas corresponding to hidden pipes or reinforcements, and characteristics such as material, diameter and depth could be identified. Separating some of these properties may require to create a different setup for the sensor, and it will be further investigated.

Figure 28. Hyperbolas identified by the GPR sensor.

The **robot navigation** is able to create the map and locate itself within it, identifying and incorporating fixed obstacles. The navigation also reacts to unknown or movable obstacles such as persons in the environment.

Figure 29. The robot navigation map.

The **dome LiDAR + RGB fusion** provides with a dense point cloud that will be used to create the semantic 3D map of the space.

In summary, we have a system, Oliwall, ready to be further tested and refined in order to acquire complete information of the demolition site. Next steps is to adjust those things that can be improved and further test the system, in laboratory and real controlled demolition sites, with two goals: providing data for the developments of WP2 and WP3, and to prepare the robot for the pilot demonstrations.

References

[Macenski:2020] S. Macenski, F. Martín, R. White, J. Clavero. [**The Marathon 2: A Navigation System**](#). IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2020.

[Macenski:2023] S. Macenski, T. Moore, DV Lu, A. Merzlyakov, M. Ferguson, [**From the desks of ROS maintainers: A survey of modern & capable mobile robotics algorithms in the robot operating system 2**](#), Robotics and Autonomous Systems, 2023.

[Nav2:2025] Github repository for Nav2: <https://github.com/ros-planning/navigation2>

[Navi-Wall:2025] Deliverable D1.2 Navi-Wall, Project Report, July 2025.

Annexes

Annex 1: Images of the robot construction and testing, and links to videos

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17WXAuj7UuNYaTnypGQknQpK54S0IYlIS?usp=sharing>

Annex 2: Software and link to repository

<https://github.com/DISCOVER-Horizon-Europe-Project>

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Oliwall User Manual 1

Oliwall: Autonomous non-invasive scanning and identification robotic system

An autonomous navigation robot package for ROS2 that performs 3D mapping using RTABMap and autonomous navigation using Nav2.

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Overview

This project provides a complete autonomous navigation solution for a differential drive robot equipped with:

- 3D LiDAR sensor (Ouster Dome or SICK)
- Two depth cameras for visual feature detection and point cloud colorization
- U10 robotic arm mounted on top for wall scanning applications
- IMU and odometry sensors

Robot Capabilities

The robot can:

1. **Map** the environment in 3D using RTABMap SLAM
2. **Navigate** autonomously within the created map using Nav2
3. **Scan walls** using the U10 arm equipped with various sensors (GPR, multispectral camera, etc.)

Sensor Configuration

Dual Camera Setup:

- Two depth cameras are mounted on the robot to assist RTABMap with:
 - **Feature detection:** Rich visual features help RTABMap build robust 3D maps
 - **Loop closure:** Visual features enable the system to recognize previously visited locations and correct drift
 - **Localization:** Improved pose estimation by fusing visual and LiDAR data
 - **Point cloud colorization:** With accurate extrinsic calibration, the cameras provide RGB information to color the 3D LiDAR point clouds, creating visually rich maps

U10 Robotic Arm:

- Mounted on top of the robot platform
- Designed for wall scanning applications
- Compatible with multiple sensor payloads:
 - Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)
 - Multispectral cameras
 - Other inspection sensors
- Enables automated wall inspection and data collection

Prerequisites

- ROS2 (Humble or later)
- RTABMap ROS
- Nav2
- Gazebo (for simulation)
- Required sensors (for real robot):
 - 3D LiDAR (Ouster Dome or SICK)
 - Two OAK-D cameras
 - Joystick controller
 - U10 arm (for wall scanning applications)

Setup

Environment Configuration

Before launching any nodes, you **must** set the `ROS_DOMAIN_ID`:

```
# For specific robot models (if using physical robots)
set_moby_model GREEN    # Sets ROS DOMAIN ID for GREEN robot
# OR
set_moby_model RED      # Sets ROS DOMAIN ID for RED robot

# OR set manually
export ROS_DOMAIN_ID=1 # Must be in range [1-19]
```

Build the Package

```
cd ~/ros2_ws
colcon build --packages-select navi_wall
source install/setup.bash
```

Launch Files

3D Mapping (`mapping_3d.launch.py`)

Creates a 3D map of the environment using RTABMap SLAM with visual-LiDAR fusion.

Purpose

- Launch the robot platform (simulation or real)
- Start RTABMap in mapping mode with dual camera support

- Enable loop closure detection using visual features
- Create colored 3D point cloud maps
- Visualize mapping process in RViz

Usage

Simulation Mode:

```
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=true world:=warehouse
```

Real Robot:

```
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=false lidar:=dome
```

Parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
sim	false	Enable simulation mode
world	warehouse	World file for simulation (e.g., warehouse, office)
lidar	dome	LiDAR sensor type (dome or sick)
oak	true	Enable OAK-D camera drivers (both cameras)
odom_tf_from_controller	false	Get odom→base_link TF from diff drive controller
rtab_viz	false	Launch RTABMap visualization tool
database_name	rtabmap	Name of RTABMap database file (saved in <code>maps/</code> folder)
log_level	warn	ROS logging level

Examples

```
# Map in simulation with visualization
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=true rtab_viz:=true

# Map with real robot using SICK LiDAR, custom database name
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=false lidar:=sick
database_name:=warehouse_map

# Map without OAK-D cameras (LiDAR-only mapping)
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=false oak:=false
```

Output

- RTABMap database saved to: `maps/<database_name>.db`
- Database contains:
 - 3D point cloud map (colored if cameras are enabled)
 - Visual features for loop closure
 - Graph-based map representation

- Use joystick to teleoperate the robot while mapping

Navigation (`move_robot.launch.py`)

Navigate autonomously within a previously created map using Nav2 with visual-aided localization.

Purpose

- Launch the robot platform
- Load a previously created map
- Start localization with dual camera support (AMCL, SLAM Toolbox, or RTABMap)
- Start Nav2 navigation stack
- Provide RViz interface for setting navigation goals

Usage

With RTABMap Localization (default - recommended):

```
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=true database_name:=rtabmap
```

With AMCL Localization:

```
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=true localizer:=amcl \
map:=warehouse_map
```

Real Robot:

```
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=false localizer:=rtab \
database_name:=warehouse_map
```

Parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>sim</code>	<code>false</code>	Enable simulation mode
<code>world</code>	<code>warehouse</code>	World file for simulation
<code>localizer</code>	<code>rtab</code>	Localization method (<code>rtab</code> , <code>amcl</code> , or <code>slam</code>)
<code>map</code>	<code>warehouse_map</code>	Map YAML file name (for AMCL/SLAM modes)
<code>database_name</code>	<code>rtabmap</code>	RTABMap database name (for RTABMap localization)
<code>lidar</code>	<code>dome</code>	LiDAR sensor type (<code>dome</code> or <code>sick</code>)
<code>oak</code>	<code>true</code>	Enable OAK-D camera drivers (both cameras)
<code>odom_tf_from_controller</code>	<code>false</code>	Get <code>odom</code> → <code>base_link</code> TF from controller
<code>rtab_viz</code>	<code>false</code>	Launch RTABMap visualization tool
<code>log_level</code>	<code>warn</code>	ROS logging level

Localization Methods

1. RTABMap (`rtab`) - Visual-LiDAR localization (recommended)

- Uses the 3D map with visual features created during mapping phase
- Best for 3D feature-rich environments
- Utilizes dual cameras for robust loop closure and drift correction
- Requires database created with `mapping_3d.launch.py`

2. AMCL (`amcl`) - Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization

- Uses 2D occupancy grid map
- LiDAR-based localization only
- Requires a `.yaml` map file in `maps/` folder

3. SLAM Toolbox (`slam`) - Simultaneous mapping and localization

- Creates/updates 2D map while navigating
- LiDAR-based only

Examples

```
# Navigate in simulation with RTABMap (visual + LiDAR localization)
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=true localizer:=rtab \
database_name:=my_map

# Navigate with AMCL on real robot
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=false localizer:=amcl
map:=office_map

# Navigate with SLAM Toolbox (mapping + navigation)
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=true localizer:=slam

# Navigate with RTABMap visualization to see loop closures
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=false localizer:=rtab rtab_viz:=true
```

Navigation in RViz

1. Launch the navigation stack
2. In RViz, wait for the map to load
3. Click "2D Pose Estimate" and set initial pose (if using AMCL)
4. Click "Nav2 Goal" and set navigation goal on the map
5. Robot will plan path and navigate autonomously
6. Visual features help maintain accurate localization during navigation

Simulation (`sim.launch.py`)

Launch Gazebo simulation environment with the robot.

Usage

```
ros2 launch navi_wall sim.launch.py world:=warehouse lidar:=dome
```

Parameters

- `world` : World name (default: `warehouse`)
 - `lidar` : LiDAR type (`dome` or `sick`)
 - `headless` : Run Gazebo without GUI (default: `false`)
-

Platform Control (`platform.launch.py`)

Low-level platform launch that starts robot hardware/simulation and sensors.

Usage

```
# Simulation
ros2 launch navi_wall platform.launch.py sim:=true world:=warehouse

# Real robot
ros2 launch navi_wall platform.launch.py sim:=false
```

Parameters

- `sim` : Simulation mode (default: `false`)
 - `world` : World file for simulation (default: `warehouse`)
 - `sick` : Enable SICK LiDAR (default: `false`)
 - `dome` : Enable Dome LiDAR (default: `true`)
 - `oak` : Enable OAK-D cameras (default: `true`)
 - `odom_tf_from_controller` : TF from controller (default: `false`)
-

Workflow

Complete Mapping and Navigation Workflow

Step 1: Create a Map

```
# Set ROS domain
export ROS_DOMAIN_ID=1

# Launch mapping (simulation) with cameras enabled
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=true \
  world:=warehouse database_name:=my_warehouse_map

# Drive the robot around using joystick to map the entire area
# The dual cameras will:
#   - Detect visual features for loop closure
#   - Colorize the 3D point cloud
#   - Improve localization accuracy
# Monitor mapping progress in RViz
# Watch for loop closures in RTABMap (if rtab_viz:=true)
# Press Ctrl+C when mapping is complete
```

The map will be saved to `maps/my_warehouse_map.db` with:

- Colorized 3D point cloud
- Visual features for localization
- Graph structure with loop closures

Step 2: Navigate in the Map

```
# Launch navigation with the created map
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=true localizer:=rtab \
database_name:=my_warehouse_map

# In RViz:
# 1. Wait for map to load (you'll see colorized point cloud)
# 2. Set navigation goals using "Nav2 Goal" tool
# 3. Robot will navigate autonomously
# 4. Visual features help maintain accurate pose estimation
```

Real Robot Workflow

```
# Step 1: Create map on real robot with calibrated cameras
export ROS_DOMAIN_ID=1
ros2 launch navi_wall mapping_3d.launch.py sim:=false lidar:=dome \
database_name:=real_environment

# Drive around with joystick until map is complete
# Ensure good camera-LiDAR calibration for accurate colorization
# Ctrl+C to stop

# Step 2: Navigate in real environment with visual localization
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=false localizer:=rtab \
database_name:=real_environment
```

Wall Scanning Workflow (with U10 Arm)

```
# Step 1: Navigate to target wall
ros2 launch navi_wall move_robot.launch.py sim:=false localizer:=rtab \
database_name:=building_map
# Set navigation goal near target wall in RViz

# Step 2: Position robot and execute wall scan
# (Wall scanning launch files and procedures to be documented)
# The U10 arm will scan the wall with mounted sensors (GPR, multispectral, etc.)
```

Planned Features

Frontier-Based Exploration

Autonomous map generation through frontier-based exploration is planned for future releases. This will allow the robot to:

- Automatically explore unknown areas
 - Build maps without manual teleoperation
 - Intelligently choose exploration targets
 - Leverage visual features for better exploration decisions
-

Important Note: Multi-Camera RTABMap Setup

⚠ CRITICAL: To support the dual-camera setup in RTABMap, you must build RTABMap from source with OpenGV support. The binary installation does not include multi-camera synchronization features.

Building RTABMap with Multi-Camera Support

Follow these steps to build RTABMap with OpenGV support:

STEP 1: Install Dependencies

```
sudo apt-get install build-essential cmake libeigen3-dev
sudo apt remove ros-$ROS_DISTRO-rtabmap* # Uninstall rtabmap binaries
```

STEP 2: Clone OpenGV

```
cd ~/
git clone https://github.com/laurentkneip/opengv.git
```

STEP 3: Build and Install OpenGV

```
cd opengv
mkdir build && cd build
cmake .. -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=/usr/local
make -j$(nproc) # If your computer has >16GB RAM. Otherwise use -j2 or -j1 (slower)
sudo make install
```

STEP 4: Clone RTABMap Core Library

```
mkdir -p ~/rtabmap_ws/src
cd ~/rtabmap_ws/src
git clone https://github.com/introlab/rtabmap.git
```

STEP 5: Build RTABMap with OpenGV

```
cd rtabmap/build
cmake .. -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=/usr/local
make -j$(nproc) # If your computer has >16GB RAM. Otherwise use -j2 or -j1 (slower)
sudo make install
```

STEP 6: Build rtabmap_ros with Multi-Camera Support

```
cd ~/rtabmap_ws
git clone --branch ros2 https://github.com/introlab/rtabmap_ros.git src/rtabmap_ros
rosdep update && rosdep install --from-paths src --ignore-src -r -y
colcon build --symlink-install --cmake-args -DRTABMAP_SYNC_MULTI_RGBD=ON \
-DRTABMAP_SYNC_USER_DATA=ON -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release
```

STEP 7: Source the Workspace

```
source ~/rtabmap_ws/install/setup.bash
# Add this to your ~/.bashrc to make it permanent
echo "source ~/rtabmap_ws/install/setup.bash" >> ~/.bashrc
```

Note: The flags `-DRTABMAP_SYNC_MULTI_RGBD=ON` and `-DRTABMAP_SYNC_USER_DATA=ON` are essential for enabling multi-camera synchronization in RTABMap.

Additional Resources

Directory Structure

```
navi-wall/
├── config/           # Configuration files for controllers, Nav2, RTABMap
│   ├── nav2_params.yaml
│   ├── rtab_ekf_params.yaml
│   └── oak_params.yaml
├── launch/          # Launch files
├── maps/            # Saved maps and databases
├── rviz/            # RViz configuration files
├── worlds/          # Gazebo world files
├── navi_wall_description/ # Robot URDF/xacro files
└── python nodes/    # Custom Python nodes
```

Key Topics

Sensor Topics:

- `/scan` - 2D laser scan
- `/points` - 3D point cloud from LiDAR
- `/camera/rgb/image_raw` - RGB camera image (camera 1)
- `/camera/depth/image_raw` - Depth image (camera 1)
- `/camera2/rgb/image_raw` - RGB camera image (camera 2)
- `/camera2/depth/image_raw` - Depth image (camera 2)

RTABMap Topics:

- `/rtabmap/cloud_map` - Colorized 3D point cloud map
- `/rtabmap/mapData` - Graph data with loop closures
- `/rtabmap/info` - SLAM statistics and loop closure info

Control Topics:

- `/cmd_vel` - Velocity commands

- `/diffbot_base_controller/cmd_vel_unstamped` - Controller input
- `/cmd_vel_joy` - Joystick velocity commands

Navigation Topics:

- `/map` - Occupancy grid map
- `/goal_pose` - Navigation goal
- `/local_costmap/costmap` - Local planning costmap
- `/global_costmap/costmap` - Global planning costmap

Arm Topics (U10):

- Topics for wall scanning operations (to be documented)
-

Appendix 2. Oliwall User Manual 2

Oliwall Desing Manual

Date	30/11/2025
Version	1.4

ATTENTION

This manual applies only to the equipment described within it. If additional equipment is incorporated to the robot, please contact UPC-CDEI.

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1. Security and recommendations

Symbols

DANGER!

Consider in any case. Warning of direct danger, which can produce severe injuries or even death

WARNING!

Consider in any case. Warns about dangerous situations, which may produce severe injuries or even death.

ATTENTION

Danger that can provoke not so severe injuries, as well as material damage to the parts.

IMPORTANT

Describes situations that may lead to damage of the machine or parts. Indicates preventive measures.

INFORMATION

Recommendations for use and applications.

1.1. General indications

Warnings and safety measures to follow.

	Before starting the equipment, read carefully the safety instructions. All users must know these recommendations.
	Consider the safety regulations of the country and particular regulations of the region, the industrial sector and the company in which it is used. (Directiva 2009/104, el Real Decreto 1215/1997 and others).

1.1.1. Introduction

This informational text has been written with the purpose that the owners, persons in charge, and users of the machine read it, understand it, and examine it carefully. The technical documentation should always be kept, in its entirety, in a place close to the machine and clearly identified.

This instruction manual draws attention to certain details of special importance for the use of the machine.

Machine malfunctions can only be avoided, and safe operation guaranteed, if this instruction manual is well understood. For this reason, it is essential that all concerned persons are aware of its existence and have read it.

We recommend an extremely thorough reading before commissioning, since we do not accept responsibility for damage, unexpected situations, or operational failures resulting from failure to follow this Instruction Manual.

If difficulties should nonetheless arise, please contact our technical department. We reserve the right to make technical modifications to what is described in this instruction manual if we consider them to be improvements to the machine.

1.1.2. Importance of the instruction manual

- This manual refers exclusively to the machine configured as described on the cover.
- The manufacturer is considered responsible for the safety, reliability, and performance of the machine only once this instruction manual has been read and understood.
- Always keep in mind that this manual has been prepared with your protection and your health and safety in mind.
- Regarding the “after-sales” phase, reading and understanding this instruction manual provides significant advantages for the customer:
 - avoiding excessive inquiries regarding doubts and operational problems.
 - preventing behaviors that could cause damage to the machine or the process.

1.1.3. Proper use

- Machines or assembly groups may only be used under the conditions intended for them. Use will only be considered compliant once the installation/assembly conformity form (prior to commissioning) and the proper-use conformity form have been completed and returned to the manufacturer.

- Any use different from or beyond what is described in this Manual will not be considered appropriate. In such cases, we will not be held responsible for any resulting damage.
- Proper use of the machine also implies:
 - following all instructions contained in the instruction manual.
 - performing all specified inspection and maintenance operations.

1.1.4. Improper use

- We will not be held responsible for damage resulting from improper use of the machine.
- Improper use means that:
 - substances or materials have been used that are inappropriate or that could cause deterioration of any installation components, or that may lead to explosions, toxic gas production, or other dangers for personnel.
 - any type of unauthorized or unspecified materials have been processed with the machine or stored near it.

1.1.5. Warranty and responsibilities

Warranty or liability claims will not be accepted in cases of personal or material damage caused by one or more of the following:

- Installation or assembly by personnel not belonging to or not authorized by the manufacturer.
- First commissioning performed by personnel not belonging to or not authorized by the manufacturer.
- Improper use of the machine.
- Incorrect adjustments, commissioning, operation, or maintenance of the machine.
- Use of the machine when the safety installations are not in perfect condition or when safety devices have not been correctly installed or are not functioning.
- Failure to follow the instructions in the manual regarding safety, transport, storage, assembly, commissioning, maintenance, and equipment of the machine.
- Self-performed modifications to the configuration of the machine.
- Insufficient monitoring of machine parts subject to wear.
- Improper repairs.

- Cases of disaster, foreign-object impact, or force majeure.

1.2. Safety instructions

1.2.1. Observe the instructions contained in the manual

- Familiarity with the basic instructions and safety standards is an essential requirement for safe and trouble-free operation of the machine.
- This instruction manual contains the most important guidelines to ensure safe use of the machine.
- The instructions in this manual—especially safety standards—must be carefully observed by all persons who will work with the machine.
- The applicable regulations in the place of use (Directive 2009/104 and others), occupational safety and health regulations, as well as stipulated inspection and maintenance tasks, must also be observed.

1.2.2. Personnel training

- Only personnel who have received the appropriate training and instructions may work on this machine.
- The scope of action for personnel—regarding assembly, commissioning, operation, equipment, maintenance, and repair—must be clearly defined.
- Personnel in training may only work with the machine under the supervision of an experienced operator.

1.2.3. Hazards related to machine operation

The machine has been manufactured according to the latest technology and legal safety requirements. However, its use may still cause serious physical injury to the user or third parties, as well as damage to the machine or other material goods. The machine may only be used:

- For its intended purposes.
- When all conditions ensuring total safety are met.
- Any malfunction that could compromise safety must be corrected immediately.

1.2.4. Workstation of the assigned operator

- Work must be carried out in front of the machine.

- The machine must never be climbed upon while in operation.
- Cleanliness and good visibility at the workstation and surrounding area must be guaranteed, with periodic checks performed.

1.2.5. Safety and protective measures

- Before every machine start-up, all safety devices must be correctly installed and operating.
- Protective mechanisms may only be removed once the machine is disconnected and accidental start-up is impossible.
- The emergency stop device must always be easily accessible.
- If the safety valve of your installation has been activated, it must be replaced without delay; otherwise, proper functioning of this safety device cannot be guaranteed.

1.2.6. Personal protective equipment and organizational measures

- The manufacturer's datasheet contains specific protective devices for the various materials and/or applications, or can be obtained after consulting the material manufacturer.
- All existing safety devices must be inspected periodically.
- The installation, including the control device and power supply, must not be located in an explosion-hazard zone.

2. Safety measures

- The instruction manual must always be kept at the location where the machine is used.
- In addition to the instruction manual, general and specific regulations on accident prevention and environmental protection must be readily available and applied.
- All safety and hazard signs on the machine must be kept in good condition and permanently legible.

3. Safety measures during normal operation

- Use the machine only if all protective devices are functioning properly.
- Before switching on the machine, ensure that no one can be affected by its operation.
- Check at least once per shift that none of the machine's safety devices show visible deterioration or any kind of neutralization or tampering.

4. Machine operation

- Under no circumstances may the software programs be modified.
- Only properly trained personnel may operate the machine.

5. Electrical hazards

- Work related to electrical supply must be carried out exclusively by specialized professionals.
- The machine's electrical equipment must be inspected periodically. Any components found to be in poor or deteriorated condition must be promptly repaired, removed, or replaced.
- The distribution cabinet must always remain closed. Access is only permitted to authorized personnel equipped with a key or the necessary tools.
- If work must be carried out on active conductive parts, a second person must always be present to operate the main switch and disconnect the machine if necessary.
- Otherwise, disconnect the machine and ensure that it cannot be restarted by mistake.
- Rotating parts and fluid media may have electrostatic charge and can cause personal injury or material damage if a potential difference occurs.
- Electrostatic discharges can impair the functionality of electronic components or damage them. Before handling electronic components, an object connected to ground must be touched.

6. Special hazard sources

- When working with solvents or caustic chemical substances, special protective measures must be taken, particularly to prevent damage to the eyes.
- For any work such as assembling, disassembling, reassembling, commissioning, operating, modifying, adjusting, or carrying out maintenance on the machine, the instructions described in the user manual must be followed.
- The machine must be switched off to carry out any of these tasks.
- All local regulations regarding safety and accident prevention are fully applicable to machine operation.

6.1. Maintenance, servicing, and troubleshooting

- Adjustment, maintenance, and inspection tasks must be carried out within the prescribed time intervals.
- Personnel must be informed before beginning maintenance and servicing work.
- It must be ensured that none of the production means or elements operating independently of the machine can be activated unintentionally, for example, compressed air or hydraulics.

- For any maintenance, inspection, or repair work, the machine must be disconnected from the power supply and the main switch secured against unexpected startup, meaning:
 - the switch must be turned off and the key removed.
 - a warning sign must be placed to prevent anyone from reconnecting the machine.
- Large modules must be carefully and securely attached to a lifting device before being replaced.
- It must be checked that no screw is loose or insufficiently tightened.
- Once maintenance work is completed, all safety devices must be checked for proper functioning.

6.2. Modifications to machine configuration

- No modifications, extensions, or alterations may be made to the machine without the express consent of the manufacturer. This requirement also applies to parts subject to wear.
- Written confirmation from us is required for all modification work.
- In case of replacement or wear, only original parts must be used. (We do not guarantee that non-original parts meet the required strength and safety specifications.)
- The machine's identification plate must not come into contact with aggressive cleaners or solvents.

6.3. Cleaning instructions

- Substances and materials must be handled and disposed of properly, especially:
 - When working on lubrication systems and devices.
 - When cleaning with solvents.
- If safety data sheets are not available, the user must obtain them and carefully follow their instructions before using these materials.
- The use of solvents or cleaning products based on halogenated hydrocarbons—such as trichloroethane or methylene chloride (dichloromethane)—may cause chemical reactions in aluminum and galvanized parts, leading to oxidation. In extreme cases, an explosion may occur due to this reaction. Therefore, only cleaning products that do not contain the above-mentioned substances may be used.
- It is strictly forbidden to light or carry fire for any purpose within a radius of five (5) meters.

7. General description of the robot

The Oliwall robot (see Figure 1) is a mobile platform with an arm manipulator (a mobile manipulator) designed to fulfill the following functions: navigate in the demolition environment, identify the elements to explore, and apply different sensors in order to determine and locate objects that can appear in the demolition site and materials that compose the different parts of the site. All this information is to be stored and transmitted to the BIM.

Figure 1. General Oliwall overview.

7.1. Main elements

As shown in Figure 2, the base consists of two motor-reducer assemblies responsible for traction and a supporting caster wheel. This part also includes the motor drivers and the pinion motor and reducer that will actuate the toothed crown located at the top. This toothed crown is responsible for rotating the upper structure with respect to the base in order to ensure omnidirectionality. Above the crown, there is a mechanism to prevent hyperstaticity. This mechanism functions similar to a universal joint, allowing two rotations and vertical movement. The upper structure can move freely relative to the base while fulfilling its function of increasing the robot's stability by serving as its support.

Figure 2. Base of Oliwall.

The metallic structure (see Figure 3) contains the battery, all the electronics and sensors necessary for the proper functioning of the robot, the UR10 controller, the UR10 lifting column, and the robotic arm itself. All these essential parts of the robot are supported in two ways. Firstly, they have four caster wheels that rest on the ground. Secondly, they are connected to the base via springs with adjustable compression. This design transfers a significant portion of the structure's weight to the driving wheels, increasing traction and reducing the load on the four auxiliary caster wheels, which primarily serve to enhance the robot's stability against movements and inclinations. Regarding the electrical power, the robot will be powered by a Deye SE-G5.1 Pro-B 51.4 V.

The scanning sensors will be positioned at the end of the UR10. The Figure 4 illustrates the placement of the sensors in its base.

Figure 3. Structure of Oliwall.

Figure 4. Scanning sensor plate.

The sensors are distributed to maximize the scanning area at the corners, using the rotation of the end part of the UR10 arm. The robot rotates the sensor's base to align the desired sensor with the corner, which requires to place the sensors at the corner of the base for better fitting.

The combination of the GPR with the depth and hyperspectral cameras provide the robot with all the required scanning capacities.

7.2. Electric system

Regarding the electrical power, the robot is powered by a Deye SE-G5.1 Pro-B 51.4 V battery. The electric circuit is shown in Figure 5, it includes the equipment used in the robot and the security elements needed for safe operation.

Figure 5. Electrical circuit of Oliwall.

The following equipment was used for the robot:

Equipment	Model
Wheel motor	BR03, Brushless, incremental encoder
Turret motor	Brushless
Turret encoder	Absolute encoder
Wheel and turret driver	IRD_EB_48/60
24 v tranformer	SD-1000L-29
Arm	UR10e
Lifting tower	Custom LINAK
UR10 control box	OEM Control Box
PC	Jetson AGX Orin
LiDAR Dome	OSDome
LiDAR Sick	multiScan100
IMU	Integrated in the Sick
Camera	OAK-D Pro W
Multiespectral Camera	Custom, Visible: 335-700 nm, no visible: 990-1700 nm
GPR sensor	GP8800
Battery	DEYE SE-G5.1Pro-B

Switch	Teltonika RUTX50
Router	Teltonika TSW030
Fan	Ventilador Axial RS PRO de 92.5 x 92.5 x 25mm, 24 V dc, 3.4W, 2900rpm, flow rate 88.3m ³ /h, 35dB
Slip ring	H2586-2410-SMT

Technical data sheet

Dimensiones generales	
Length	814 mm
Width	612 mm
Base height	1950 mm
Maximum height	3200 mm
Weight	275 kg
Maximum path slope	30%
Rated power	2,3 kW
Nominal consumption	33 A
Maximum consumption	54 A
Battery	51.4 VDC
Maximum speed	1 m/s
IP Protection grade	IP 52C

8. Design justification

Now it is briefly justified why this is the design and the inconveniences or possible solutions that have been proposed throughout the design.

8.1. Previous requirements

The design was based on the condition that the robot had to scan up to a height of 3 meters and also the floor, which implies the need to have some element of elevation of the end of the arm (UR10).

It was also mandatory that the robot could be moved within an old building with narrow doors of 70 cm and corridors of 90 cm, and climb stairs or ramps.

8.2. Dimensions

Starting from the second requirement, a 60x60 robot is proposed but a problem arises, and that is the axis of the wheels had to be very close to the central axis, so that when the upper part rotated with respect to the lower one, the wheels did not touch the walls or they passed in size, that is, the robot could not rotate on itself in narrow places like corridors.

Seeing this impediment, it is decided that through corridors, the robot would not rotate on itself, but the UR10 moves to scan all parts. Here arises the idea of lengthening the robot to gain stability in case of facing a ramp and in the displacements through these spaces. This is how the current dimension is established, which is the maximum that can

pass through a corridor that rotates an angle of 90° , which is the limiting one (explained in Concept Design).

Another key element is the height of the robot that is related to the position of UR10. The maximum height is marked by the ability of UR10 to scan the ground without interfering with the base of the robot. Here the approximate height limit was set and it has been seen that it is not an inconvenience to position the rest of the elements of the robot, the space in this case is not a problem.

8.3. Choice of UR10

With the intention of scanning the walls, ceiling and floor of a building, an element that brings sensors closer to these positions is needed. From the beginning a cobot was chosen to do so. Options were proposed between Universal Robot and Doosan, and between different models that affected the weight that could be carried to the end (depending on the sensors used) and the work lengths they had. With this data, and without knowing exactly the weight of the sensors, UR10 was chosen for economic and characteristics issues that best adapted to the whole. There was the possibility of a larger robot that would not have to raise it to touch the roof but the length of the arms could cause interference in narrow places such as corridors.

8.4. Elevation of the UR10e

Once it is decided that the UR10e is used and must be raised, the LCi3 column is selected. It is a special column for UR10e, sized to work with it, with software to integrate with UR10 and of all extensible lengths.

8.5. Position of the toothed crown and battery

At the beginning it was based on a design where the battery was at the bottom and the crown at the top, so that the inertia to move was lower and the center of mass was lower. Due to the size of the robot, the battery had to be on the engines, since at ground level it no longer fits due to the limitations of space despite having made the longitudinal axis longer. This would make the whole of the base higher and position the crown higher. The problem arises with the elevation of UR10, which, being a standard column, had to be positioned as low as possible to ensure that the robot could scan the ground. This interfered with the crown, therefore, in order to maintain sizes and scanning requirements, it is decided to lower the crown as much as possible and position the battery at the top.

8.6. Stability and structure

The robot is tall and narrow, and despite having in mind to put the 4 caster wheels at the ends, the movements with the arm raised imply some instability risks. Because of this, the robot has been made longer than previously thought.

On the other hand, the soil will present pebbles, dirt and obstacles, and it can be an irregular soil. That is why it is decided to implement a system that allows keeping the top of the robot stable and avoiding indeterminacy by having 7 wheels in contact with the ground. In this way we ensure that the motor wheels are always in contact with the

ground, being independent of the 4 casters. The joint between these two systems is a Cardan joint that allows two rotations, plus the vertical rotation given by the crown.

Finally, this cardan type system incorporates springs in the vertical axis of the mechanism to transmit part of the weight of the upper part to the area of the base. Having the battery and many heavy elements above limits the traction of the wheels. The springs transmit most of the force to the driving wheels, allowing the structure to be lighter and the normal in the four caster wheels to be small. This spring system can be regulated with a thread that preloads the springs and can control which normal is to be transferred between the base and the structure.

8.7. LiDARs layout

For navigation it is decided to use two LiDARs placed at two opposite ends diagonally in order to minimize the number of LIDARS required and maximize the field of view. Once this decision is made, it is necessary to decide the height of these. From the viewing area defined by the manufacturer, the option of placing them at the bottom of the structure, at the height of the battery, or as they are now, at the top is proposed. Placing them in the lower area makes it difficult to manufacture the structure, makes it more complex and apart from it it will be necessary to modify battery measurements in order to be able to place everything. The elevated column also makes this positioning difficult. If the LiDAR is placed in the lower area, the view of it is limited to the upper part, since the floor is clearly seen, but vision is lost in the upper area. For these reasons, it is decided to place the LiDARs in the upper area. This creates a dead zone on the diagonals where there is no LiDAR and hence no distance to obstacles information. To limit this, 3D printing supports that slightly tilt the LiDAR are incorporated, modifying the vision area and favoring to be able to observe the areas closest to the robot.

8.8. Base set

The base set follows the patented design at CDEI-UPC. The housing is a welded and watertight piece where wheel sets and caster wheel are assembled.

The distance between a wheel and the center of the robot is the same as the distance between the motor axis and the vertical axis. This fact is important for the kinematics of the robot (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Base set.

As observed, the distribution at the base is as compact and simplified as possible. The wheel motors share a common axis and incorporate their own encoders.

The base also contains two IRD drivers. The motor of the vertical axis is connected in L, in order to reduce the height of this part, and not to interfere with slipping or with the connectors. The idea of this piece is to facilitate assembly and interaction with the robot, making connections accessible from the outside but being covered at the same time.

Figure 7. Assembly of the crown gear.

In Figure 7, we observe the assembly of the crown gear, which already has all the incorporated components, encoder, reducer of the crown and its driver and connectors. It can be seen how removing the lid allows accessing all the wiring from the outside without having to dismantle anything and once it is finished everything is covered again. All this pack is mounted on the base with 6 M8 screws with riveted nuts.

Ventilation has been incorporated into the base area to prevent possible heating of the drivers and the area in general.

8.8.1. Wheel set

The wheel set is used in all the patented CDEI-UPC robots and only the rim (red piece) is modified. The wheel in this case will have a 7075-T6 aluminum rim (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Wheel set.

The motor selection has been realized considering the heavy torques required in irregular terrains. The BR3 motor torque is mainly limited by the reducer, which can offer 60 Nm of nominal traction and about 100 Nm of maximum torque, sufficient for the needs of the robot.

It should be noted that the incorporation of cycloidal and harmonic reducers has been explored but their efficiency is lower and the choice is also limited by the length of the set, since the dimensions of the robot are narrow and to maintain the appropriate kinematic structure. The best option is a planetary reducer that can be placed within the support of the wheels.

It should also be noted that the type of wheel to be placed influences a lot, if it is with rim or rolling band and of what type. Blickle provided the friction coefficients of the materials, and based on this information we decided to use rubber to obtain more traction, reduce the weight of the steel rim, and gain space by manufacturing our own rim in 7075-T6 aluminum.

Coeficiente de Rozamiento			
Suelo	Softahne Bestahne Soft	Extrathane Besthane	Goma
Acero seco	$\mu > 0,3$	$\mu > 0,25$	$\mu > 0,60$
Acero húmedo	$\mu > 0,10$	$\mu > 0,08$	$\mu > 0,40$
Hormigón liso, seco	$\mu > 0,3$	$\mu > 0,25$	$\mu > 0,60$
Hormigón liso, húmedo	$\mu > 0,10$	$\mu > 0,08$	$\mu > 0,40$
Asfalto seco	$\mu > 0,25$	$\mu > 0,20$	$\mu > 0,50$
Asfalto húmedo	$\mu > 0,05$	$\mu > 0,05$	$\mu > 0,3$

Figure 9. Friction coefficient.

8.8.2. Crown drive

The crown gear set is supplied by ISB. Outer teeth are chosen for packaging issues, since in order to pass a slipping a very large and heavy crown would be necessary in case of interior teeth. First, the EB1.14.0179.400-2SPPN was chosen, which was cheaper because it did not have the hardened tooth, in principle, and smaller. This gave problems to be

able to lubricate and do the maintenance, since, due to the disposition that had the connection to fatten it, it is very difficult to access. To solve the problem, we move on to the EB1-1-0188-200-3RTTN, which has a much more comfortable assembly with threaded, not-through holes, and the greaser is very accessible. The downside is that the tooth is hardened by induction and a hardened pinion is also needed to increase its duration. On the other hand, the tooth has positive displacement and is module 4, which are not available for standard pinions; therefore, it will be necessary to manufacture a non-standard pinion.

8.8.3. Electronics

The layout of electronics within the base has already been briefly discussed. The following explains the electronic components used.

For the drivers, Infranor's recommendation for the acquired motors were the IRD drivers, which allow connection to both CAN and EtherCAT.

As for the encoder, the design calls for an absolute multi-volt encoder of about 8000 steps/rev resolution and compatible with EtherCAT.

The Penlink slip ring used has the smallest hollow shaft PSH-X25 (see Figure 10).

Model	No. Of Circuits			Length
	Total	2A	10A/15A	
PSH-X25-6P	6	-	6	55 mm
PSH-X25-12S	12	12	-	55 mm
PSH-X25-12P	12	-	12	79 mm
PSH-X25-6P/12S	18	12	6	79 mm
PSH-X25-24S	24	24	-	79 mm
PSH-X25-18P	18	-	18	103 mm
PSH-X25-12P/12S	24	12	12	103 mm
PSH-X25-6P/24S	30	24	6	103 mm
PSH-X25-36S	36	36	-	103 mm
PSH-X25-24P	24	-	24	127 mm
PSH-X25-18P/12S	30	12	18	127 mm
PSH-X25-12P/24S	36	24	12	127 mm
PSH-X25-6P/36S	42	36	6	127 mm
PSH-X25-48S	48	48	-	127 mm

Figure 10. Penlink offer of sliprings.

All the electronics for the robot actuators can be commanded with 12 inputs. The overall maximum current is in theory 144 A, but because of the limitation of 108 Nm per wheel, and with the transmission ratio of 25, we have 4.3 Nm at each motor, which is equivalent to 31 A each approximately. Using 12 cables of 15 A peak would suffice.

8.8.4. Deflector

Even though the demolition sites are manually emptied, it is very possible that the ground could be very dirty with stones or other debris. A deflector is designed consisting of a folded aluminum sheet and screwed to the base with riveted nuts. It is easy to put on and take off and allows large objects not to be stuck in the caster wheels.

8.8.5. Ventilation

Since both the base and the structure will be closed areas, there is the possibility that the cooling is not good, since it is only dissipated by contact between aluminum and steel and then steel with outside air. In the face of this concern, fans are installed, one in the base and one in the structure, together with its filter, to improve cooling if necessary. It is arranged so that the air is ejected backwards for the base case and downwards for the structure with the filter at the other end.

8.8.6. Cardan type mechanism

As irregular terrain is expected and much of the weight is high, it is intended to prevent contact from being lost with the outer wheels that are responsible for stability, so a mechanism is designed to adapt to the terrain. This allows two rotations (excluding the one made by the crown) and a vertical displacement controlled by two springs in parallel. Thus, the structure follows the irregularities of the terrain.

Figure 11. Mechanism adaptable to irregular terrain.

The main function of the springs is to transmit the force of the mass of the structure, which is elevated, towards the base area, in order to increase the traction and reduce friction of the 4 casters of the structure by making it virtually lighter. Thus, regulating the preload of the springs regulates the normal force that the 4 casters and the motor wheels will have.

The option of a robot that can climb stairs has been discarded, but if it is necessary to prepare the robot for more standard ramps, therefore, allowing vertical movement allows to climb ramps more easily. This vertical movement is guided by two aluminum axes and specific ball corridors so that they can withstand the axial load corresponding to the weight of the structure, that is, they are oversized and are very long to avoid play problems.

8.9. Structure and platform

8.9.1. Welded structure

The welded structure is designed with commercial profiles of welded steel to simplify the system and is structured in two floors. The first to accommodate the heaviest things and be the first area above the base. The second is responsible for hosting electronics. The problem is to accommodate the lift column, which to get the robot to touch the ground can not be very high or very low, since, when rotating Cardan can interfere with the base. This is how it is placed where the limit of the two restrictions is. A structure is also made above to hold the column on top and release part of the moment supported by the lower support, so a lid can also be placed on top to protect the robot.

8.9.2. Covers

To comply with the tightness requirements and also make ventilation efficient, covers are incorporated into the whole structure. The side part is simple two-folded covers that form the side part and the other two sides covered with a laser cutting aluminum sheet. All the plates are attached to the structure through incorporated riveted holes and small separators to maintain distances and envelop the LiDARs. In the battery area there are two differentiated covers. One to be able to remove and put the battery and the other to be fixed.

For the lower part, a base plate is made collated in the structure to transmit the wiring towards the slip ring, and this sheet is collated to two more complex small plates that follow the shape of that area.

At the top a rubber seal may be used against water and in the rest of areas such as the LiDARs part or the bottom you must put some silicone or composite material that seals the small open areas to avoid external elements. If the concern is the water there should be no problems with just using the rubber at the top.

8.9.3. Battery

The custom battery, wider and lower than the standard ones, can be attached to the sides of the structure with screws and is easier to place.

The calculation of consumption is excellent and it is verified that with the characteristics of this battery is enough. It is located in the lower part of the structure to lower the center of mass of the whole system.

8.9.4. Electronic layout

Figure 12. Electronic layout.

8.9.5. Scanning sensors

The GPR works by being in contact with the floor or in proximity, less than 10 mm. However, the hyperspectral camera needs between 50 and 60 mm of distance with the wall in order to align the direction of the light and the camera. For that the supporting structures are designed to ensure each sensor works with its desired distance.

Figure 13. Scanning sensors.

The RGB camera needs a clear view with no obstacles, and it can not be blocked by the other sensors. Given that it has a 150-degree FOV, the camera needs a high elevation support to ensure that the GPR does not block its view.

Given the high elevation, the camera will be in proximity with the wall during the operation of the GPR. If the surface of analysis is not flat that could be a potential source of damage to the camera. That is why it will be prioritized that the camera is aligned with the GPR, so it can block irregularities (see Figure 13).

9. Manufacturing

Generally, for the assemblies that will be done by hand or with basic tools, an H7-f7 is specified. For fits with bearings, etc. the tolerance indicated by the manufacturer is chosen.

In the case of the welded base, the axes of the motors need to be carefully aligned. The perpendicularity between the axes of the wheels and the axis of the vertical rotation must be ensured.

In the case of the structure, the position of the plate that will join the base set with the Cardan is specified, so that the structure is centered. The rest of the tolerances in the sub-assemblies welded, are aimed at ensuring that the structure maintains perpendicularities and flatness.

On the other hand, 7075-T6 aluminium is chosen for mechanized parts under requirements to reduce weight and have good mechanical characteristics. The axes of the Cardan are made of F114, to ensure proper functioning. For the sheet metal parts, common steel is used in case of future welding.

10. Assembly

The assembly procedure of each of the subassemblies is presented below.

10.1. Base set (D)Base)

10.1.1. Wheel set (D)B)Wheels)

Below is a section view of the set.

Figure 14. Wheel set.

The whole rim (red piece) and the rolling band are press fitted by Private Mechanized. It should be remembered that before pressing the system, it is necessary to put adhesive on the surface of the rim and the rolling band that will be in contact. Previously, the two surfaces must be cleaned and then "REMAXX ANTI-GLISS-LUBE" should be applied, which is what the manufacturer recommends. The assembly is presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Assembly of the wheel.

The bearings are fitted in the housing by using a soft hammer. Then we introduce the axis with the reducer set. It is fixed axially with the Seeger and then the rest of the elements are assembled.

Cardan set (D)B)cardan)

Figure 16. Cardan set.

The upper rotation axis is mounted first. The bearings are inserted outside the guide (d'b'c'guia). Next, it is necessary to position the axis1 (d'b'c'eix1) and the two dowel pins (d'b'c'dolla) within the guide (d'b'c'guia), so that there is space to be able to enter the axis2 (d'b'c'eix2) on one side. The shaft is introduced on one side, and then it is put into the shaft and circlip at the other end to fix it axially. Finally, the fit pin must be introduced at the bottom.

Figure 17. Cardan assembly.

The pads are mounted on the supports (d'b'c'support), introduced on the axis and assembled with the three screws each on the "d'b'c's".adapt". Finally, the shaft and slip ring are mounted on the central part with the M10 screw.

10.1.2. Crown set (D (B_corona (v2)

This set is very simple; insert and tight all the screws in the way they appear in the drawing. The crown gear has a centering pin to align with the base (d.b.c.base.v2) (see Figure 18).

Figure 18. Crown set.

10.1.3. Final set

Once these parts are assembled, you can proceed to assemble the overall base. In order to do so, join the different parts as shown in the model. Special attention must be paid to the positioning of the whole crown on the welded base, which must be left as aligned as possible. It is not recommended to dismantle this junction very often, since the distance between the motor axis and the vertical rotation axis of the robot are modified each time, then the control system could be affected.

Figure 19. Final set.

Remember that extra holes have been left in the area of the caster wheel for the case of needing to modify the caster to add a double wheel. If that is not the case, they need to be covered.

10.2. Structure set

Follow the indications in the drawing and model for the assembly using screws. Remember to watch over the positioning of the lift column. Space has been left at the top to facilitate placement. Then the 3D-printed pieces (d'stopper'elevator) are placed to fix the whole set. It is also observed that the covers have separators, there are rubber separators of various sizes in the market but to streamline the processes, it is preferred to manufacture them in 3D in plastic. It is also recommended to glue them in order to extract the covers easily without losing pieces in between. At the top, rubber seals are presented to seal the top cover.

The supports for the electronic components, the Control Box and the Jetson are made of wood to reduce load and they are connected to the structure with 3d printed unions. Providing flexibility for multiple adaptations and making the design highly modular.

10.3. Final set

To unite the two parts, it is necessary to enter the guides of the Cardan (d.esguiascardan) into the linear ball bearings and also on the Cardan set with its springs. It is recommended to lift the part of the structure with a platform so that the springs do not act. Then, this guide is placed inside the linear bearings and the structure is lowered. If the elevation of the structure can be controlled the height would be much more comfortable. Finally, the structure is dropped and is already mounted. Remember that the pre-tension of the springs is adjustable and controls the transfer of load between structure and base. It is necessary to ensure that the two springs are located at the same height.

11. Utilization

Please see software guide.

12. Maintenance

One of the parts that requires occasional lubrication is the ring gear, which has two lubrication holes on the top for injecting oil or grease. The company ISB specifies the type of grease to use and the frequency. The gear teeth and the pinion must also be lubricated with a high-viscosity grease. This is a specific grease; you can use one available at the UPC-CDEI or purchase it. To renew or top it up, you should contact a specialist or rely on the UPC-CDEI's expertise.

Regarding the wheel assembly, it features protected, self-lubricating bearings; therefore, at most, the bearings would need to be replaced in the event of failure or malfunction. Otherwise, no maintenance is required.

As for the electronics, dust must be removed from the components, and ventilation filters must be cleaned once they become clogged. The filters should be monitored continuously to detect dirt accumulation. Inside the robot, where the electronics are housed, it is recommended to clean surface dust and component fans annually. Based on recommendations for electronic devices such as computers, this maintenance interval is extended because the components have double protection: firstly, the ventilation of the robot's covers and, secondly, their own housing which may have built-in ventilation, as is the case with the UR10 controller. If possible, a cleaning frequency of every 6 months would be excellent.

12.1. Weekly maintenance

Perform a visual inspection of the following machine parts:

Traction wheels:

- 1) Check the condition of the wheel's polyurethane coating. If significant tears or irregular wear appear, proceed with replacement.
- 2) Check the wheel diameter; the nominal dimension is 200 mm. If diameter decreases exceeding 5 mm are observed, proceed with replacement.
- 3) Check that the diameters of the traction wheels have a difference of less than 0.5%. Otherwise, evaluate if the orthogonal movements are correct.

Visual inspection of bolted joints:

- Check for loose screws.
- Check for parts with movement relative to other non-moving parts of the robot. In case of detecting any bolted joint with play, proceed to apply the corresponding tightening torque.

12.2. Monthly maintenance

1) Lubrication

Grease the vertical axis crown and grease the bridge wheels.

2) Belt tension

Check the tension of the traction wheel transmission belt. Apply a force of 5.5 N (see Figure 5.6) at the point equidistant from the belt's tangent with each of the pulleys. If the deflection is greater than 3.5 mm, proceed to adjust the belt tension.

3) Bridge clearance

- Check the transverse clearance of the bridge articulation. If the bridge is rotated about an imaginary vertical axis and the total displacement of the end of the bridge with respect to the chassis is greater than 5 mm, the bridge articulation bearings must be replaced.
- Check for dirt on the moving parts of the machine and proceed to clean them.

12.3. Maintenance limited by operating time

The following components are limited by cycles or operating hours.

- **Battery:** After 3,000 full charge cycles, the battery must be replaced with a new one.
- **Traction wheel transmission:** After 20,000 operating hours, the belt and wheel reducer assembly must be replaced.